

Effect of hydrogen-ion concentration on stability of 1 : 1 complex of iron(III) with salicylic acid and its different derivatives

Sunanda Das^a and M. C. Chattopadhyaya^b

^aC. M. P. Degree College, Allahabad-211 002, India

^bElectrochemical Sensor Laboratory, Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad, Allahabad-211 002, India

E-mail : mcc46@rediffmail.com, tulip_125@ indiatimes.com

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The stability constant of 1 : 1 Fe^{III} complex of salicylic acid and ten other derivatives of the ligand was determined by spectrophotometric method developed in this laboratory at different pH values, after taking care of hydrolysis of Fe^{III}. It was found that during complex formation both hydroxyl and carboxyl group releases the hydrogen ion.

Iron(III) due to its pronounced affinity for ligands containing oxygen forms several coloured complexes with salicylic acids. Thus salicylic acid and sulfosalicylic acid have extensively been used as colorimetric reagent for iron(III). Ogawa and Tobe¹ have reported formation of different complexes at different pH values for the salicylic acid and sulfosalicylic acid with Fe^{III} ion. They have calculated the stability constants of 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 complexes. According to them the higher complexes are formed at higher pH values. In their work Ogawa and Tobe have considered the release of proton from both carboxyl and hydroxyl groups. However, Park² has considered the release of hydrogen ions from carboxyl group only. He has reported a protonated complex. Similar observations were made by Agren^{3,4}. In his doctoral thesis Novikov⁵ has considered the release of both the protons during complex formations but has not experimentally demonstrated the release of both the protons.

In order to resolve this controversy the present work was undertaken in which besides salicylic acid and 5-sulfosalicylic acid, nine different derivatives of salicylic acid were taken. As Fe^{III} undergoes hydrolysis in the acid range of pH, the effect of hydrogen ion concentration on the stability constant was also studied. Experiments were so designed to conclusively prove how many protons are released in the complex formation.

Results and discussion

If one considers the reaction between Fe^{III} and salicylic acid as,

after omitting the charges for simplicity, the equilibrium

constant for the reaction (1) can be expressed as

$$k_1'' = \frac{[\text{Fe H}_{2-n}\text{L}] [\text{H}]^n}{[\text{Fe}] [\text{H}_2\text{L}]} \quad (2)$$

If we define k_1' as $[\text{Fe H}_{2-n}\text{L}]/\{[\text{Fe}][\text{H}_2\text{L}]\}$ then we can write eqn. (2) as

$$\log k_1'' = \log k_1' + n \log [\text{H}] \quad (3)$$

or

$$\log k_1' = \log k_1'' + np [\text{H}] \quad (4)$$

Therefore, if one plots $\log k_1'$, which is apparent stability constant and depends on pH, against $p[\text{H}]$, then the slope will be the value of n i.e. the number of protons released during the formation of 1 : 1 complex.

The k_1' values were determined at different pH values (Table 1) calculated using the method described earlier⁶. The $p[\text{H}] = -\log [\text{H}]$, calculated from charge and mass balance. These values agree well with the values obtained by the conversion of pH-meter reading using McBryde's method⁷.

When $\log k_1'$ values were plotted against $p[\text{H}]$ a straight line of slope slightly less than 2, was obtained in each case. The points corresponding to higher $p[\text{H}]$ values do not fall on this line. As an example the plot for Fe^{III}-3-methyl-5-sulfosalicylic acid system is given in Fig. 1. It seems at higher pH value the hydrolysis of uncomplexed Fe^{III} is taking place. Therefore it is necessary to introduce a correction factor (CF) which is given by⁸ $(1 + k_h/[\text{H}])$, where k_h is the first stage hydrolysis constant for Fe^{III}, the value⁹ of k_h being 2.34×10^{-3} at ionic strength of 0.1. When the logarithm of $k_1' (1 + k_h/[\text{H}])$ was plotted against $p[\text{H}]$, points corresponding to

Table 1. $\log k'_1$ and $\log k'_{1.CF}$ values of Fe^{III} salicylate complexes at different pH

$I = 0.1 M, M^\circ = L^\circ = 2.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

	Ligand ($\lambda_{mn}, \log \epsilon_c$)	p[H]												
		1.39	1.52	1.69	1.84	1.98	2.18	2.32	2.34	2.54	2.58	3.06	3.18	
1.	SA	$\log k'_1$	2.94	3.22	3.54	3.72	4.01	-	-	4.64	-	5.00	-	5.52
	(530, 3.22)	$\log k'_{1.CF}$	2.96	3.25	3.59	3.80	4.11	-	-	4.82	-	5.28	-	6.17
2.	3-MSA	$\log k'_1$	2.58	2.86	3.16	3.52	3.71	-	-	4.33	-	4.64	-	5.26
	(556, 3.30)	$\log k'_{1.CF}$	2.60	2.89	3.20	3.58	3.80	-	-	4.52	-	4.92	-	5.92
3.	4-MSA	$\log k'_1$	-	3.09	3.44	3.68	3.95	4.33	-	4.61	-	4.95	-	5.67
	(534, 3.30)	$\log k'_{1.CF}$	-	3.12	3.48	3.75	4.03	4.46	-	4.78	-	5.22	-	5.32
4.	5-MSA	$\log k'_1$	-	3.15	3.45	3.74	3.99	4.34	-	4.62	-	4.97	-	5.60
	(560, 3.32)	$\log k'_{1.CF}$	-	3.18	3.50	3.80	4.08	4.48	-	4.80	-	5.24	-	6.25
5.	5-NSA	$\log k'_1$	3.83	4.07	4.30	4.44	4.73	-	5.10	-	-	5.22	-	5.42
	(496, 3.47)	$\log k'_{1.CF}$	3.85	4.09	4.35	4.51	4.81	-	5.28	-	-	5.50	-	6.98
6.	5-CSA	$\log k'_1$	3.29	3.52	3.81	4.06	4.29	4.60	-	4.76	-	5.01	-	5.28
	(536, 3.48)	$\log k'_{1.CF}$	3.31	3.55	3.86	4.13	4.38	4.74	-	4.93	-	5.29	-	5.94
7.	5-SSA	$\log k'_1$	2.46	2.72	3.00	3.25	3.47	-	3.97	-	4.13	-	4.50	-
	(506, 3.31)	$\log k'_{1.CF}$	2.49	2.75	3.05	3.31	3.55	-	4.14	-	4.39	-	5.06	-
8.	3-M, 5-SSA	$\log k'_1$	3.20	3.43	3.75	-	4.20	-	-	4.73	-	-	-	5.30
	(530, 3.36)	$\log k'_{1.CF}$	3.22	3.46	3.80	-	4.29	-	-	4.91	-	-	-	5.96
9.	4-M, 5-SSA	$\log k'_1$	3.37	3.60	3.90	4.16	4.32	4.60	-	4.76	-	4.95	-	5.26
	(510, 3.48)	$\log k'_{1.CF}$	3.40	3.64	3.94	4.22	4.41	4.73	-	4.94	-	5.22	-	5.92
10.	3-S, 5-MSA	$\log k'_1$	3.59	3.80	4.11	4.30	4.47	4.69	4.83	-	4.96	-	5.18	-
	(546, 3.40)	$\log k'_{1.CF}$	3.61	3.84	4.16	4.36	4.55	4.82	5.00	-	5.23	-	5.75	-
11.	3-Hg, 5-SSA	$\log k'_1$	-	2.86	3.14	3.40	3.61	3.85	4.07	-	-	4.33	-	4.70
	(514, 3.48)	$\log k'_{1.CF}$	-	2.89	3.19	3.47	3.70	3.98	4.24	-	-	4.61	-	5.35

Fig. 1. Effect of pH on apparent equilibrium constant of Fe^{III} -3-methyl-5-sulfosalicylic acid.

higher p[H] value not only falls on the straight line but the value of the slope equals to 2, which shows the release of

both the protons of salicylic acid and its derivatives during 1 : 1 complex formation with Fe^{III} . Similar observations were made with other ligands.

Experimental

Reagent grade samples of the following salicylic acids were employed : (i) 2-hydroxybenzoic acid (SA) (B.D.H.), (ii) 2-hydroxy 3-methylbenzoic acid (3-MSA) (B.D.H.), (iii) 2-hydroxy 4-methylbenzoic acid (4-MSA) (K and K Lab), (iv) 2-hydroxy 5-methylbenzoic acid (5-MSA) (K and K Lab), (v) 2-hydroxy 5-nitrobenzoic acid (5-NSA) (Fluka), (vi) 2-hydroxy 5-chlorobenzoic acid (5-CSA) (Fluka), (vii) 2-hydroxy 5-sulfobenzoic acid (5-SSA) (E. Merck), (viii) 2-hydroxy 3-methyl 5-sulfobenzoic acid (3-M, 5-SSA), (ix) 2-hydroxy 4-methyl 5-sulfobenzoic acid (4-M, 5-SSA), (x) 2-hydroxy 3-sulfo 5-methylbenzoic acid (3-S, 5-MSA), (xi) 2-hydroxy 3-mercury 5-sulfobenzoic acid (3-Hg, 5-SSA). Where M stands for $-CH_3$ group, N for $-NO_2$, and C for $-Cl$ group. The acids (viii) to (xi) were prepared as described earlier¹⁰.

All the acids were purified by several recrystallization before use. Aqueous solutions were prepared by direct weighing, using CO_2 free water. A stock solution of ferric

chloride in dilute HClO_4 was prepared and standardized titrimetrically against standard dichromate solution. CO_2 free NaOH and HClO_4 solutions were used for bringing the pH at the desired value. Solutions of acids and alkalis were standardized by conventional titrimetric methods. NaClO_4 was used as a background electrolyte.

All pH measurements were made with a Universal pH meter (Redelkis OP-204, Hungary) with glass and calomel electrodes. The absorption spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 137 UV-Vis or SF-4 USSR spectrophotometer. Measurements were done at room temperature at $25 \pm 1^\circ$.

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